

Spiro Heterocycles. Part-VIII. Synthesis, Herbicidal and Fungicidal Activities of some New Fluorine-containing Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(1'*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole]-5'-carbonitriles/carboxyethylesters

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A number of fluorinated spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(1'*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole]-5'-carbonitriles/carboxyethylesters have been synthesised and tested for their herbicidal and fungicidal activities. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by ir, pmr and elemental analyses.

THE indole nucleus plays an important role as a common denominator for various biological activities. Indole itself has been found to possess tuberculostatic¹, psychotropic², fungicidal³ and bactericidal⁴ activities. Indole-2,3-dione prolongs hexabarbital narcosis in mouse, antagonises electric shocks or pentylenetetrazole induced tonic convulsions and inhibits MAO in liver homogenates⁵. Pyrazole nucleus is also present in a number of drugs like novalgin, antipyrine and aminopyrine. These observations prompted us to synthesise some new compounds possessing both pyrazole and indole nucleus joined via a pyran ring through a spiro-carbon atom.

In the present study, we report the synthesis, herbicidal and fungicidal activities of fluorine containing spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(1'*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole]-5'-carbonitrile/carboxyethylester. Indole-2,3-diones (1) were prepared by literature methods⁶⁻⁸. Indole-2,3-dione with malononitrile/ethylcyanoacetate in presence of piperidine as catalyst resulted in the formation of 3-dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethyleneindol-2-one (2)⁹ which on nucleophilic attack of the active methylene of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone, afforded spiro[3*H*-indole-3,4'(1'*H*)-pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole]-5'-carbonitriles/carboxyethylesters (3)¹⁰ (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

Spectral studies: Ir spectra of compound 2 (X=5-F, R=H, R'=COOC₂H₅) reveal absorption at 3 300 (NH), 1 710 and 1 680 (C=O), weak absorption at 1 610 (C≡N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C). In pmr spectra, a triplet centred at δ 1.17 for CH₃ protons, a quartet centred at δ 4.2 (CH₂), a multiplet at δ 7.6-6.8 (ArH) and a singlet at δ 8.9 (NH) are observed.

In the ir spectra of 3b a doublet at 3 040 and 3 300 cm⁻¹ represents respectively, the 'free'

Scheme 1

asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching due to NH₂ group. A singlet at 3 100 cm⁻¹ due to NH stretching and two carbonyl absorptions at 1 680 and 1 660 cm⁻¹ are also observed. In pmr spectra, a singlet due to CH₃ protons of 3'-position at δ 1.58, triplet due to CH₂ protons centred at δ 0.8, a quartet for CH₂ protons centred at δ 3.84 and a multiplet for aromatic protons in the region of δ 6.6-7.8 alongwith a singlet at δ 10.08 for NH and at δ 7.9 for NH₂ protons are observed. ¹⁹F nmr spectra showed a singlet for fluorine atom attached to indole ring at δ -106 ppm with reference to hexafluorobenzene as external reference. The proposed structure has been confirmed on the basis of mass spectra, which showed a molecular ion peak at 434 (M⁺) and M+1 peak at 435, corresponding to the molecular formula C₂₂H₁₉FN₄O₄ (Table 1).

Herbicidal activity: It is observed from Table 2 that none of the compounds are active against grass (*Panicum crusgalli*) in pre- as well as post-emergence under submerged conditions. Compounds are also

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,4'(1'H)-PYRANO[2,3-c]PYRAZOLE]-5'-CARBONITRILES/
CARBOXYETHYLESTERS (3)*

Compd. no.	X	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	203	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄
3b	5-F	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	211	68	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ FN ₂ O ₄
3c	6-F	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	219	72	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ FN ₂ O ₄
3d	5-F	COCH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	138	66	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O ₅
3e	6-F	COCH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	177	55	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ FN ₂ O ₅
3f	5-F	H	ON	226	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₃
3g	6-F	H	ON	221	63	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₃
3h	5-F	CH ₂ N	COOC ₂ H ₅	150	69	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ FN ₂ O ₄
3i	5-F	CH ₂ N	COOC ₂ H ₅	165	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ FN ₂ O ₄
3j	4-CF ₃	H	COOC ₂ H ₅	237	62	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ F ₃ N ₂ O ₄
3k	4-CF ₃	H	ON	214	55	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₂ O ₃

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

TABLE 2—HERBICIDAL ACTIVITY* OF SPIRO[3H-INDOLE-3,4'(1'H)-PYRANO[2,3-c]PYRAZOLE]-5'-CARBONITRILES/
CARBOXYETHYLESTERS (3)

Compd. no.	Under submerged condition			Broad leaved weeds	Dosage kg/ha	Under up-land condition**					
	Dosage kg/ha	Grass (<i>P. crusgalli</i>)				Pre-emergence				(E)	(F)
		Pre-emergence	Post-emergence			(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)		
3d	10	1	1	4	10	1	1	1	1	1	1
	1	1	1	1	10	1	1	1	1	1	1
	10	1	1	4	10	1	1	1	1	1	1
3i	1	1	1	2	10	1	1	1	1	1	1
	10	1	1	3							
3j	1	1	1	1	10	1	1	1	1	1	1
	10	1	1	4							
3k	1	1	1	2	10	1	1	1	1	1	1
	10	1	1	4							

*Rating : 5 = Complete kill, 1 = No control.

**Weeds/crops : (A) = Japanese radish, (B) = Sugar beet, (C) = Germinated soyabean, (D) = *Polygonum blumei*, (E) = *Digitaria adscendens*, (F) = *Panicum crusgalli*.

inactive under up-land conditions. All the compounds are, however, active against broad leaved weeds. Compounds 3d, 3i and 3k exhibit above 80% effect at 10 kg/ha. Compounds 3i and 3k are effective even at a very low concentration (1 kg/ha).

Fungicidal activity : Compounds 3d and 3i-k were also tested for fungicidal activity against *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* and *Phytophthora infestans*. None of them was found to show any activity.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin - Elmer 557 spectrophotometer, pmr and ¹⁹F nmr spectra on a Jeol FX-90Q using TMS as internal reference for pmr and C₆F₆ as external reference for ¹⁹F nmr, and mass spectra on a MS-30 and MS-50 Kratos spectrometer.

5/6-Fluoroindole-2,3-diones (1) : The compounds were prepared by literature methods⁶⁻⁸.

3-Dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethyleneindol-2-one (2) : A mixture of 5/6-fluoroindole-2, 3-dione

(0.17 mol) and malononitrile/ethylcyanoacetate (0.17 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) containing piperidine (2-3 drops) as catalyst was refluxed for 3 h⁹. After being chilled overnight, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with ether (10 ml) and recrystallised from ethanol as violet needles.

Spiro[3H-indole-3,4'(1'H)-pyrano[2,3-c]pyrazole]-5'-carbonitriles/carboxyethylesters (3) : A solution of 3-dicyano/carboethoxycyanomethyleneindol-2-one (0.01 mol) and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was treated with piperidine (2 drops) and was stirred at room temperature for 4 h¹⁰. After the removal of ethanol the residue was rinsed with dichloromethane and the insoluble solid recrystallised from ethanol to colourless crystals, which were homogeneous on tlc (Table 1).

Evaluation of biological activities : The herbicidal activity of four representative compounds (3d, 3i-k) was evaluated. Table 2 illustrates the degree of reactivity against weeds/crops tested under submerged or up-land condition during October 14 and November 15 at a dosage of 1 and 10 kg/ha :

Submerged condition : effect of compounds on grass (*Panicum crusgalli*) and annual broad leaved weeds was tested; *up-land condition* : effect on various crops Japanese radish, sugar beet, soyabean germs and weeds, *Polygonum blumei*, *Digitaria adscendens* and *Panicum crusgalli* was tested.

For fungicidal screening, spore suspension (5 ml) of each test organism (72 h culture) was added to sterilised potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium (100 ml) at 35–40° by thorough shaking. The petriplates were seeded with the mixture and the paper disc of ethanolic solution of compound (1% of absolute ethanol) and the reference compound, (mycostatin) were placed in it. The petridishes were incubated at 30° for 48 h. The zone of inhibition was considered as an indicator for activity. All the experiments were in five replicates. The effect was studied on *Cochiliobolus miyabeanus* and *Phytophthora infestans*.

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